

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101007990.

Project Acronym:	VITALISE
Project Title:	Virtual Health and Wellbeing Living Lab Infrastructure
Project Number:	101007990
Topic:	Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme INFRAIA-02-2020 Integrating Activities for Starting Communities
Type of Action:	RIA - Research and Innovation action
Start date of the Project:	April 2021
Duration of the Project:	36 months

D11.3 Evaluation procedure and accepted proposals

(Version 3.0, 30/11/2023)

Disclaimer: The information in this document reflects only the author's views and the European Community is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained therein. The information in this document is provided "as is" without guarantee or warranty of any kind, express or implied, including but not limited to the fitness of the information for a particular purpose. The user thereof uses the information at his/ her sole risk and liability.

Copyright message: ©VITALISE Consortium, 2021. This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both. Reproduction is authorised provided the source is acknowledged.

D11.3 Evaluation procedure and accepted proposals

Deliverable:	D11.3 Evaluation procedure and accepted proposals	
Work Package:	WP11	
Due Date:	30/11/2023	
Submission Date:	30/11/2023	
Lead Beneficiary:	SIT	
Version:	3.0	
Status:	submitted	
Author name(s):	Giulia Onorati (SIT), Valentina Conotter (SIT), Erica Fazzini (SIT)	
Contributor(s):		
Reviewer(s):	Despoina Petsani (AUTH)	Giulia Campodonico (ENoLL)
Approved by:	Evdokimos Konstantinidis (ENoLL), Project Coordinator	
Keywords:	Transnational Access, Virtual Access, Open Calls, Management, Living Labs	
Nature:	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> R – Report <input type="checkbox"/> P – Prototype <input type="checkbox"/> D – Demonstrator <input type="checkbox"/> O - Other	
Dissemination level:	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> PU - Public <input type="checkbox"/> CO - Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission) <input type="checkbox"/> RE - Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

The **VITALISE** Consortium consists of:

Participant #	Participant organisation name	Short Name	Country
1 (Coordinator)	EUROPEAN NETWORK OF LIVING LABS IVZW	ENoLL	Belgium
2	ARISTOTELIO PANEPISTIMIO THESSALONIKIS	AUTH	Greece
3	LAUREA-AMMATTIKORKEAKOULU OY	LAUREA	Finland
4	THOMAS MORE KEMPEN VZW	LICALAB	Belgium
5	FUNDACION INTRAS	INTRAS	Spain
6	TREBAG SZELLEMI TULAJDON- ES PROJEKTMENEDZSER KORLATOLT FELELOSSEGU TARSASAG	TREBAG	Hungary
7	ASOCIACION DE INDUSTRIAS DE CONOCIMIENTO Y TECNOLOGIA - GAIA - EUSKALHERRIKO EZAGUTZA ETA TEKNOLOGIA INDUSTRIEN ELKARTEA	GAIA	Spain
8	FUNDACION CENTRO DE TECNOLOGIAS DE INTERACCION VISUAL Y COMUNICACIONES VICOMTECH	VICOM	Spain
9	ETHNIKO KENTRO EREVNAS KAI TECHNOLOGIKIS ANAPTYXIS	CERTH	Greece
10	AIT AUSTRIAN INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY GMBH	AIT	Austria
11	SOCIALIT SOFTWARE E CONSULTING SRL	SIT	Italy
12	UNIVERSIDAD POLITECNICA DE MADRID	UPM	Spain
13	WITA SRL	WITA	Italy
14	ANTHOLOGY VENTURES JSC	AV	Bulgaria
15	VILABS OE	VILABS	Greece
16	FORUM DES LIVING LABS EN SANTE ET AUTONOMIE	LLSA	France
17	TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITEIT INDHOVEN	TUE	Netherlands
18	ROYAL INSTITUTION FOR THE ADVANCEMENT OF LEARNING MCGILL UNIVERSITY	McGill	Canada
19	UNIVERSITE DE MONTREAL	UDEM	Canada

D11.3 Evaluation procedure and accepted proposals

Revision history			
Version	Date	Modified by	Comments
0.1	10/10/2023	SIT	Table of Content
0.2	25/10/2023	SIT	Fill required information and request feedback
1.0	21/11/2023	SIT	Version ready for review
2.0	25/11/2023	AUTH, ENOLL	Reviews
3.0	29/11/2023	SIT	Final version to be submitted

Table of Contents

TABLE OF CONTENTS	5
LIST OF FIGURES	6
LIST OF TABLES	6
ABBREVIATIONS	7
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	8
1 INTRODUCTION	9
1.1 THE VITALISE PROJECT.....	9
1.2 PURPOSE OF THE DOCUMENT.....	9
2 DESIGN OF THE EVALUATION PROCEDURE OF THE OPEN CALLS FOR TRANSNATIONAL ACCESS	10
2.1 ELIGIBILITY EVALUATION.....	11
2.2 FEASIBILITY EVALUATION.....	12
2.3 SCIENTIFIC EVALUATION.....	12
3 CALLS FOR EXTERNAL RESEARCH PROPOSAL EVALUATORS	13
3.1 DESIGN OF THE EVALUATION PROCEDURE.....	14
3.2 RESULTS OF THE EVALUATIONS.....	14
3.3 ENROLMENT AND PAYMENT PROCEDURES.....	15
4 OPEN CALL FOR TRANSNATIONAL ACCESS	16
4.1 MITIGATION STRATEGIES.....	17
4.1.1 2 nd Open Call.....	17
4.1.2 3 rd Open Call.....	17
4.2 RESULTS OF THE 1 ST OPEN CALL FOR TRANSNATIONAL ACCESS.....	18
4.3 RESULTS OF THE 2 ND OPEN CALL FOR TRANSNATIONAL ACCESS.....	19
4.4 3 RD OPEN CALL FOR TRANSNATIONAL ACCESS.....	20
4.5 FINAL RESULTS OF THE OPEN CALLS FOR TRANSNATIONAL ACCESS.....	22
5 TA MANAGEMENT	26
6 TA MONITORING ACTIVITIES	28
7 APPLICATION PROCEDURE FOR VIRTUAL ACCESS	28
8 CONCLUSIONS	29
APPENDICES	30
APPENDIX 1 – TEMPLATE ELIGIBILITY EVALUATION.....	30
APPENDIX 2 – TEMPLATE FEASIBILITY EVALUATION.....	33
APPENDIX 3 – TEMPLATE SCIENTIFIC EVALUATION.....	35
APPENDIX 4 – TEMPLATE NOTIFICATION ACCEPTED PROPOSAL FOR TA.....	38
APPENDIX 5 – TEMPLATE NOTIFICATION REJECTED PROPOSAL FOR TA.....	39
APPENDIX 6 – TEMPLATE FOR THE EVALUATION OF THE APPLICANTS FOR THE EXTERNAL EVALUATORS.....	40
APPENDIX 7 – TEMPLATE NOTIFICATION EVALUATION PROCEDURE CANDIDATE EXTERNAL EVALUATOR.....	42
APPENDIX 8 – CONTRACT AGREEMENT FOR EXTERNAL EVALUATORS.....	43
APPENDIX 9 – TEMPLATE INVOICE OF THE EXTERNAL EVALUATORS.....	48
APPENDIX 10 – INFOPACK FOR TA.....	49
APPENDIX 11 – TEMPLATE CERTIFICATE OF ATTENDANCE TO TA AND FTTP.....	58
APPENDIX 12 – DECLARATION FOR TA CANCELLATION.....	59
APPENDIX 13 – ADDENDUM TO THE CA FOR TA.....	60
APPENDIX 14 – APPLICATION MANUAL V4.1: VA SECTION UPDATED.....	61

List of Figures

FIGURE 1 EVALUATION FLOW OF THE OPEN CALL FOR TA	10
FIGURE 2 GENDER DISTRIBUTION OF THE SELECTED EXTERNAL EVALUATORS	15
FIGURE 3 EDUCATIONAL QUALIFICATION OF THE SELECTED EXTERNAL EVALUATORS	15
FIGURE 4 EDUCATIONAL BACKGROUND OF THE SELECTED EXTERNAL EVALUATORS	15
FIGURE 5 WORKING FIELD OF THE SELECTED EXTERNAL EVALUATORS	15
FIGURE 6 NATIONALITY OF THE SELECTED EXTERNAL EVALUATORS	15
FIGURE 7 SCREENSHOTS TAKEN DURING THE WORKSHOP FOR THE SCIENTIFIC EVALUATION...	16
FIGURE 8 SELECTED RESEARCHERS AND EXPECTED RESEARCHERS PER EACH LL	23
FIGURE 9 NUMBER OF TEAMS PER TEAM MEMBERS	24
FIGURE 10 AVERAGE SCIENTIFIC SCORE PER OPEN CALL	24
FIGURE 11 GENDER DISTRIBUTION OF SELECTED APPLICANTS	24
FIGURE 12 WORKING DOMAIN OF SELECTED APPLICANTS THROUGH THE 3 OPEN CALLS	25
FIGURE 13 WORKING DOMAIN OF SELECTED APPLICANTS	25
FIGURE 14 WORKING COUNTRY OF SELECTED APPLICANTS	26
FIGURE 15 GEOGRAPHICAL DISTRIBUTION OF NATIONALITIES OF SELECTED APPLICANTS	26

List of Tables

TABLE 1 STRUCTURE OF THE OPEN CALLS FOR TRANSNATIONAL ACCESS	17
TABLE 2 RESULTS OF THE 1 ST OPEN CALL FOR TRANSNATIONAL ACCESS	18
TABLE 3 RESULTS OF THE 1 ST CUT-OFF OF THE 2 ND OPEN CALL FOR TRANSNATIONAL ACCESS..	19
TABLE 4 RESULTS OF THE 2 ND CUT-OFF OF THE 2 ND OPEN CALL FOR TRANSNATIONAL ACCESS .	20
TABLE 5 RESULTS OF THE 1 ST CUT-OFF OF THE 3 RD OPEN CALL FOR TRANSNATIONAL ACCESS..	21
TABLE 6 RESULTS OF THE 2 ND CUT-OFF OF THE 3 RD OPEN CALL FOR TRANSNATIONAL ACCESS .	22
TABLE 7 RESULTS OF THE 3 RD CUT-OFF OF THE 3 RD OPEN CALL FOR TRANSNATIONAL ACCESS .	22
TABLE 8 NUMBER OF SELECTED APPLICATIONS AND RESEARCHERS	23

Abbreviations

EC	European Commission
EvB	Evaluation Board
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
H2020	Horizon 2020 Program of the European Commission
LL	Living Lab
OC	Open Call
RIL	Research Infrastructure Leader
TA	Transnational Access
TAM	Transnational Access Manager
VA	Virtual Access
WP	Work Package

Executive summary

This document reports on the design of the evaluation procedure of the VITALISE Open Calls for Transnational Access (TA), all the data about the received and the accepted proposals through the 3 Open Calls, and the design of the application procedure for Virtual Access (VA).

In the first part of the deliverable, the whole design of the evaluation procedure of the 3 Open Calls for Transnational Access is presented in great detail. The defined evaluation procedure consisted of 3 evaluation steps:

- Eligibility evaluation and assessment of the priority criteria;
- Feasibility evaluation;
- Scientific evaluation.

Evaluation criteria and templates have been defined for each stage and attached in appendix.

The following section describes the Calls for External Research Proposal Evaluators launched between M11-M12 (Feb-Mar '22), before the opening of the 1st Open Call, and at M24 (Mar '23) to enlarge the external evaluators' pool ahead of the 3rd Open Call. Some statistics related to the selected External Evaluators are illustrated.

The document proceeds with a description of how the 3 Open Calls for Transnational Access were effectively implemented between M12 and M28 of the project (Mar '22 – Jul '23), with detailed information about each application submitted. Particular attention is dedicated to illustrate the mitigation strategies that have been designed and implemented in close collaboration with WP13 and with all the Consortium to improve the attractiveness of the Open Calls. Next, the most relevant statistics pertaining to accepted project proposals and selected researchers are shown. Following the conclusion of the three calls, a collective total of 58 proposals were submitted. Remarkably, 54 of these submissions successfully met the criteria and were approved, surpassing the initial goal and resulting in the recruitment of a total of 113 researchers. This allowed us to successfully reach the KPI1.1, targeting >100 researchers recruited. Such result demonstrated the successful application of mitigation strategies throughout the 3 Open Calls tailored to maximise the number of applications, and, in turn, the number of recruited researchers.

Afterwards, the following sections detail the Transnational Access management and monitoring activities that have been defined at M24 (Mar '23) to properly report the activities and costs related to each TA project.

Finally, the document briefly explains how the application procedure for Virtual Access on the VITALISE Discovery Portal was designed, referring to D11.1 Material for Open Calls for all the information about the effectively implementation of the procedure.

1 Introduction

1.1 The VITALISE Project

Researchers in the Health and Wellbeing domain need 1) convenient access to research infrastructures, 2) direct engagement of people in order to validate hypotheses, co-design solutions and services, evaluate their feasibility and effectiveness and participate in the translation and mobilization of outcomes and 3) experience from multidisciplinary domains (e.g., healthcare management, assistive technologies, data science) to deal with the complexity of health and wellbeing research.

Over the last few years, Living Labs have emerged as resilient research and innovation infrastructures and have proved to be key to the integration of research and innovation processes in real life settings, focusing primarily on people and their engagement in research procedures. VITALISE opens up Living Lab Infrastructures as a means to facilitate and promote research activities in the Health and Wellbeing domain in Europe and beyond by enabling in-person Transnational Access to 17 Living Lab research infrastructures and by supporting remote digital access to datasets (Virtual Access) of rehabilitation, transitional care and everyday life activities through harmonized processes and common tools. VITALISE will design and develop ICT tools for shared access of similar devices and applications used across Living Labs, as well as for collecting, storing and sharing datasets. Lastly, VITALISE will invest in the development of Training methods towards the wider understanding and valorisation of Living Lab methodologies in the research community.

1.2 Purpose of the document

The objective of this document is to report all the information about the design of the evaluation procedure of the Open Calls for Transnational Access (TA), all the data about the received and the accepted proposals and the information about the design of the application procedure for Virtual Access (VA). The entire design of the evaluation procedure has been largely discussed and designed by the consortium partners in weekly meetings to optimize the communication flow within WP11 Calls for ideas and proposals, experiment selection.

Regarding TA, all the WP11 activities have been carried out in strong synergy with the related WPs and, whenever necessary, the weekly meetings have been extended to all the LLs and to other relevant partners to thoroughly discuss how to organize the Open Calls, the whole evaluation process and the management of the TA. All the informational material available for applying to the Open Calls for TA were deeply described in D11.1 Material for Open Calls, while the Application toolkit for applying for TA was described in D11.2 Application toolkit.

Moreover, WP11 worked in closed collaboration with WP8, 9 and 10 to support the management of the TA to the LLs for all three Open Calls, by:

- Setting up all the information for conducting the TA;
- Managing the calls to discuss the needed material (Contract Agreement, expectations/evaluations questionnaires, reports);
- Managing the flow of information;
- Monitoring the regular VA deployment, also by supporting the LLs in the production of correct and complete reporting documents.

This deliverable briefly explains all the actions and tasks that have been taken to ensure that all the LLs have the tools to manage and monitor the implementation of TA.

As far as the VA is concerned, within WP11 the procedure for applying for VA was defined, working in close collaboration with WP3 Implementation, improvement and optimized use of the H&W Living Lab Research Infrastructure Tools. In D11.1 all the available informational material regarding the VA and the information about how to apply for VA through the VITALISE Discovery Portal are described. It is worth noting that the VA application procedure has been updated in the Application manual after the D11.1 delivery, as the VA has been finalized afterwards.

2 Design of the evaluation procedure of the Open Calls for Transnational Access

The evaluation procedure that has been defined consists of 3 evaluation steps:

1. Eligibility evaluation and assessment of the priority criteria;
2. Feasibility evaluation;
3. Scientific evaluation.

Evaluation criteria and templates have been defined for each stage (detailed below). Figure 1 shows in details the whole flow of the evaluation procedure, from receipt of proposals until notification of the results.

Figure 1 Evaluation flow of the Open Call for TA

The whole selection flow was managed by SIT, being the Transnational Access Manager (TAM): VILABS received the application through the Online toolkit (see D11.2 Application toolkit) and forwarded them to SIT, who conducted the **eligibility** evaluation and checked the priority criteria. Once the **eligibility** evaluation has passed successfully, the applications have been forwarded to the Research Infrastructure Leaders (RILs) of the infrastructures selected by the applicants (up to three infrastructures per application) to evaluate the **feasibility** of the proposed study. In case an application resulted “not feasible” in any of the chosen infrastructures and if the applicants agreed to be reallocated if needed, the application was forwarded to all the other RILs to verify the possibility of carrying out the research within one of their infrastructures. In the event that the application was feasible in at least one facility, it was approved for the next step.

The last step of the evaluation procedure was the **scientific** evaluation, which was conducted by the Evaluation Boards (EvBs), that evaluated the soundness of the research proposals. The EvBs are

composed of three people: 1 expert within the consortium holding a PhD and 2 external independent experts selected through the Calls for External Research Proposal Evaluators. The internal experts were required to hold a PhD, as a research background was necessary to be able to evaluate the proposals. However, if the expert belonged to a LLs, such background was given for granted and this requirement could be not fulfilled. External experts' applications were evaluated by an internal committee, based on the resume and a motivational letter (all the information related to the involvement of the external experts are described in Chapter 3).

At the end of the evaluation procedure, SIT prepared all the documents (signed by the project coordinator) to inform the applicants about the results of the evaluation and VILABS forwarded them via email to the Leaders of the applications. In case of negative outcome of any of the three steps in the evaluation, the document would state the reason why the application had been rejected and, whenever possible, invite applicants to resubmit a new proposal in the next Open Call or the next cut-off of the same Open Call. In case of positive outcome of the scientific evaluation, the leaders of the winning applications received a communication announcing in which infrastructure they could conduct the TA. In Appendix 4 and 5 an example of the above-mentioned documents. All the people involved throughout the entire evaluation process acted independently, eventually converging in the final ranking.

The first version of the evaluation procedure (MS7) was published at M12 (Mar '22) on the project website and was described in detail in the "VITALISE Project's Application Manual to the Open Calls for Transnational Access to Research Infrastructures (Version 1.0, March 2022)" (henceforth Application Manual). Detailed information about the Application Manual and its update are available in D11.1.

2.1 Eligibility evaluation

The following profiles were eligible for TA: academic researchers, industrial researchers, government researchers, master's students, entrepreneurs, and Living Lab practitioners.

The eligibility criteria were slightly modified during the three Open Calls to allow greater participation by the various eligible profiles (see par. 4.1 about the mitigation strategies). Based on the final version of the Application Manual, the applicants have to meet the following eligibility criteria:

- They should work in an institution established in a Member State of the European Union or in a state associated to H2020 Programme [Check the [List of countries eligible for funding](#)]. Researchers working in other countries can apply but they cannot represent more than 20% of the total number of researchers that will access the VITALISE facilities;
- They cannot have Russian or Belarusian origin;
- They must work in a country other than the country where the infrastructure is based, as the Access is "Transnational". If the researchers work in a country where one of the Living Labs is located, the researchers will not have access to that specific Living Lab;
- They must disseminate the results and knowledge they will generate during the access to the Living Lab, unless it goes against the legitimate interest of their organization (see paragraph 8);
- Collaborative applications from teams and/or institutions is strongly encouraged. The expenses for each team will be covered based on the number of researchers in the team;
- If the leading applicant is a master's student, at least 1 member of the team must hold a master's degree and act as supervisor of the TA (he/she/they could join the TA fully remote)
- They should be fluent in English;
- An undergraduate/bachelor student can perform TA under the supervision of the leading applicant; in this case, the leading applicant must be either professor or postdoc affiliated to university or research centres. Transnational access is in fact provided to research teams led by a leading applicant and composed by up to 5 researchers.

A research team can apply for TA asking to visit more than one Living Lab to conduct its study. In this case, the research team must submit more than one complementary application, duly justifying their choices in the submitted application templates.

Moreover, a set of priority criteria has been defined ensuring to prioritise applicants who:

- Have not previously used the infrastructures;
- Are working in countries where no equivalent research infrastructure exists;
- Ensure scientific excellence and fully embrace Open Access policies, as promoted by the European Commission. However, also access to industrial research studies are admitted (no more than 20% of total approved projects), in order to sustain commercialization services and grant full synergies and collaboration between academic and industrial sectors;
- Have not direct link with the VITALISE consortium: applications coming from applicants from institutions that are linked to the consortium and that are considered eligible, feasible and with a scientific evaluation above the threshold will be accepted only if there are still free TA positions available after accepting all other successful applications;
- Finally, 10% of the TA positions will be reserved to refugee researchers of Ukraine.

The Transnational Access Manager (TAM) checked the proposal for meeting the eligibility criteria and for the priority criteria using a dedicated template (Appendix 1). In case of incomplete proposals or ineligible applicants, the TAM immediately got in touch with the applicant in order to verify whether the ineligibility was a matter of fact or whether it was due to errors in filing the application: this was also applied as a mitigation strategy to increase the number of successful application and widen the participation to TA. Only proposals compiled correctly and without field missing were considered eligible.

2.2 Feasibility evaluation

Eligible applications were forwarded to the corresponding Living Lab Research Infrastructure partners (up to three) for the feasibility check. During this step, the feasibility of the proposed studies was checked by the RIL against the following:

- Can the Living Lab Research Infrastructure provide the required access?
- Can the Living Lab Research Infrastructure provide the required services?
- Can the Living Lab Research Infrastructure support the study in terms of end-users recruitment?

Moreover, the RILs were asked to check, to the best of their knowledge, the truthfulness of the following 2 declarations of the applicants and to confirm if they embrace Open Access policies, as required by the Application Manual (with due exceptions mentioned in par. 2.1):

- To the best of your knowledge, have the applicants previously used the infrastructure?
- Do the applicants work in countries where, as long as you know, no equivalent research infrastructure exists?
- Do the applicants ensure scientific excellence and fully embrace Open Access policies?

The RILs used a dedicated template to evaluate the feasibility of the applications (Appendix 2). During this phase, the RILs could contact the applicants asking for some clarification regarding the services, tools and support requested by the infrastructure. At the end of all the evaluation process, applicants who submitted unfeasible proposals, received a communication with a note explaining the reasons of the rejection. The note included a short comment from all the RILs chosen by the applicant/s. If applicable, the note also included some suggestions of changes to apply to the proposal in order to successfully apply at the next Open Calls. Positively evaluated proposals were sent to the EvBs for the scientific evaluation.

2.3 Scientific evaluation

Feasible applications were evaluated by the EvBs. Each evaluator assessed the scientific soundness of the application independently of the other two evaluators in charge of the same

application, by using a dedicated template (Appendix 3). Before starting the scientific evaluation, a document with the full list of all candidates was shared with all evaluators, both internal and external ones, to check for any conflicts of interest. Based on this, the EvBs were created, and the applications assigned. The evaluation was performed on a scale from 1 to 10, according to the guide provided within the template based on the following weighted criteria:

1. Scientific and technical quality of the proposal: Is the current <i>state of knowledge</i> in the research area well described? Are <i>cited references</i> relevant and reflect the state-of-the-art? Is the proposed topic of <i>high scientific quality</i> and does it provide innovative aspects? Are the <i>research objectives</i> and expected deliverables/outputs of the proposal clearly stated? Are they <i>achievable</i> ? To which extent do the expected results <i>lead to a progress beyond the current state-of-the-art</i> ? Is a clear concept presented on how the gathered <i>data will be collected, shared, analysed, and published</i> ?	30%
2. Quality of the work plan: Is the work plan <i>adequate</i> ? Is it <i>clearly described</i> and well defined? Can the proposed work plan <i>be realized</i> in the set time? Are the scheduled tasks and methods <i>adequate to the set objectives</i> ? Is it clearly stated which <i>methods and equipment</i> will be employed? Does the proposed project <i>maximise the use of the infrastructure</i> ? Has the proposal <i>assessed any likely risks</i> ?	25%
3. Scientific qualification/track record of the proposing PI and user group: Background/track record of the <i>PI</i> , Background/track record of the <i>scientific team</i> , Are the <i>roles and responsibilities of the scientific team</i> clearly stated? Is the <i>combined expertise</i> suitable to achieve the research objective?	10%
4. Innovation: What currently unmet need/s do the innovative aspect/s address, and for whom? How do they differ from existing tools or practices? Does the proposal present a significant departure from current practice? Can the proposal provide a demonstrable improvement (time, resources, cost, effectiveness) over current methods/tools? Are the results (tools or practices) suitable for commercialization and exploitation outside the context of a research environment? Can the proposal lead to the development of a substantially new product or service?	15%
5. Collaboration with international/national partners/industry: To what extent are new European user groups with limited access to Living Labs infrastructure integrated? To what extent is the proposed project embedded into larger research programmes on a national, EU or international level? What is the potential for a long-term integration/collaboration on an international level? Are collaborations with industry envisaged?	10%
6. Training of young scientists/public outreach: How many young scientists and students at PhD level and below will be involved? Are there dissemination activities, addressing the general public, planned?	10%

After collecting all scientific evaluations, the average of the three evaluations made by each EvB was calculated and all applications were ranked in descending order based on both such scientific score and the priority criteria. Finally, each application was assigned to the chosen infrastructure accordingly.

3 Calls for External Research Proposal Evaluators

In order to create the EvBs, 2 calls for selecting the external experts were launched. The first Call for External Research Proposal Evaluators was launched between M11-M12 (Feb-Mar '22), before the opening of the first Open Call. At M24 (Mar '23) a second call was launched to increase the number of external evaluators for the third Open Call. This choice was motivated by the increasing trend in the number of submitted proposals registered between the 1st and the 2nd Open Call. It was decided to recruit more External Research Proposal Evaluators, in order to be able to timely and smoothly manage the scientific evaluation in the frame of the 3rd Open Call. A multi-faceted dissemination strategy was adopted, leveraging both formal project communication channels and

the personal connections of consortium partners to ensure that information about the calls was widely disseminated, reaching as many potentially interested individuals or entities as possible. In particular, partners were not only expected to share information through their formal channels but were also encouraged to take a more personal approach. This involved partners proactively reaching out to their own contacts who might be interested in the calls, thus effectively generating and widening interest and engagement.

3.1 Design of the evaluation procedure

The applicants for the role of External Research Proposal Evaluators were evaluated by an internal committee, based on the resume and a motivational letter. Experience in the following domain was evaluated:

- In the Health & Wellbeing domain;
- In the Living Lab methodology;
- In managing research infrastructures;
- In technology and innovation;
- In academic achievement with relevant publications;
- As an evaluator.

6 VITALISE partners (ENoLL, GAIA, LiCalab, AUTH, AV and LAUREA) composed the Board for the selection of the external evaluators. The Full board was divided in 2 groups, each of which evaluated half of the proposals. The experience criteria and the motivation letter were scored from 0 to 2 using a dedicated template (Appendix 6) and acceptance was based on a majority criteria as follows:

- If the majority (2 out of 3 evaluators) scored the application with >10 points, this was accepted;
- If the majority gave <7 points, it was rejected;
- If the majority gave between 8 and 9, the application was discussed by the Full board during a dedicated meeting. The two Full Boards met respectively on April 21st, 2022 (1st Call for External Evaluators) and on April 20th, 2023 (2nd Call for External Evaluators).

3.2 Results of the evaluations

Through the two calls for External Research Proposal Evaluators, a total of 16 evaluators were recruited. Within the first Call a total of 19 applications were submitted, 11 of which were approved (58%). In the Second Call, a total of 11 applications were submitted, 5 of which were approved (45%). All the applicants were informed of the results of the evaluation via email using a dedicated template (Appendix 7). In case of rejection, a brief comment was provided to justify the negative outcome of the evaluation.

Analysis of the data related to the recruited External Evaluators shows the predominance of female representation, sectoral distribution, prevalence of PhD holders, and diversity among technical, humanities and medical fields in both calls. Indeed, in terms of gender distribution, in the first call, 7 females (64%) and 4 males (36%) were selected, while the second call had 4 females (80%) and 1 male (20%). Overall, females constituted the majority with 11 individuals (73%), and males accounted for 5 individuals (27%) (Fig. 2). Regarding educational qualifications, the majority, 11 individuals (73%), held Ph.D. degrees, while 4 individuals (27%) had master's degrees (Fig. 3). In the domain breakdown, 4 individuals (24%) specialized in technical fields, 7 (42%) had humanistic backgrounds, and 5 (30%) had medical expertise (Fig. 4). In terms of sectoral background, the first call included 4 participants (36%) from the private sector and 7 participants (64%) from the public sector, whilst the second call had no representation from the private sector. Combining both calls, 12 individuals (71%) came from the public sector, and 4 individuals (29%) had a background in the private sector (Fig. 5).

To conclude, Figure 6 shows the geographical distribution of External Evaluators across several European countries. Spain leads with the highest number of individuals, accounting for 4

participants, followed by the UK, Italy and Portugal, each bringing 2 evaluators, while the remainder are represented by one single person. This multinational composition not only underscores the broad reach of the recruitment process but also suggests a varied perspective and expertise drawn from different cultural and educational backgrounds. The inclusion of External Evaluators from a range of countries enhances the overall richness and global perspective of the VITALISE evaluation process.

Figure 2 Gender distribution of the selected External Evaluators

Figure 3 Educational qualification of the selected External Evaluators

Figure 4 Educational background of the selected External Evaluators

Figure 5 Working field of the selected External Evaluators

Figure 6 Nationality of the selected External Evaluators

3.3 Enrolment and payment procedures

After completing the evaluation of the profiles and reporting the results of the first Call for External Research Proposal Evaluators, the accepted candidates were invited to participate in a short workshop (June 1st 2022) organized and presented by SIT and ENoLL, in which the evaluators were briefly introduced to the VITALISE project, the Open Calls, the evaluation procedure, the criteria

used, and then went into detail about how the scientific evaluation works and what was their role (internal evaluators were also invited to attend the event). In Figure 7 sample screenshots taken during the workshop.

Figure 7 Screenshots taken during the workshop for the Scientific Evaluation

The slides of the workshop were shared with the participants as well as links to the video recording. The video recording of the workshop was also shared with the newly recruited External Evaluators after the conclusion of the evaluation procedure of the 2nd Call for External Evaluators.

Before starting the scientific evaluation procedure of each Open Call, the external evaluators signed a contract drafted by ENoLL, consistent with all other contracts produced within the project, which specified what they were expected to do, the period in which they were required to conduct the evaluations, and the material they would have received to conduct the evaluation. The latest version of the contract is available in the Appendix 8. Upon completion of the scientific evaluation, external evaluators were required to issue an invoice to receive payment for the service performed (€30 per evaluation) using their own format or a template provided by ENoLL (the latest version is available in Appendix 9).

4 Open Call for Transnational Access

Three Open Calls were designed and implemented consecutively starting from M12 to M28 of the project. Table 1 illustrate the deadlines for the 3 Open Calls for TA as they were effectively implemented.

As planned, the 1st Open Call was opened at the beginning of M12, with a 2 months' window for submission (at the end of M13), to which an additional 10-day extension was then added to allow for more submissions. The results of the evaluation procedure were notified at M16 and the selected applicants were put in contact by the TAM with the reference RILs in order to organize the TA to the LLs. In this 1st Open Call, 6 applications were submitted, 4 of which were approved.

To increase the Open Call attractiveness, the 2nd Open Call was anticipated at M18 (instead of M20) in corresponding of a networking event (OLLD in Turin, Italy) attended by many partners of the consortium and it was closed at M20, reaching an overall submission window of almost 4 months. To get applicants to submit their application during the whole submission period (instead of sending their application during last days) the 2nd Open was structured with 2 cut-offs: at the end of M19 and at the end of M20. Applicants at the first cut-off were evaluated first, increasing their approval probability and being able to start the TA earlier. The 2nd cut-off, initially expected to close November 30th 2022, was then extended to January 8th 2023 to increase the number of submissions. Upon request of the applicants, an additional extension (+8 days) of the submission window was secured. The 2nd Open Call registered an increased number of applications, 23, 22 of which were approved.

The 3rd Open Call, initially structured in two cut-offs, opened March 1st 2023 (M24). The submission window was initially planned to last 2 months (Mar-Apr '23) but was later extended to May 31st 2023 (M26), to allow more submissions and to give the consortium more time to effectively disseminate the Open Call. These strategies allowed reaching the KPI1.1 "Number of total researchers recruited for transnational access: >100 researchers". By M27, 112 visiting researchers were recruited to visit

the research infrastructures. The KPI1.1 had been thought as the sum of a minimum of ca. 6 applicants for each of the 17 infrastructures of the VITALISE consortium. However, at the end of the 2nd cut-off, this internally set KPI was not reached by two infrastructures. Even if the overall KPI1.1 had been met and in order to allow to achieve also the internally set KPI, it was decided to open a 3rd cut-off, that ran between June 19th and July 16th, where only the interested research infrastructures were targeted. At the end of the 3 cut-offs, the 3rd Open Call registered 29 applications in total, 28 of which were approved.

Open Calls for TA	First Call	Second Call	Third Call
Submission	1 Mar – 30 Apr '22 +10 days	1 st cut-off: 20 Sep – 31 Oct '22 2 nd cut-off: 1 Nov '22 – 8 Jan '23 + 8 days (16 Jan '23)	1 st cut-off: 1 Mar – 2 Apr '23 2 nd cut-off: 3 Apr – 30 Apr '23 + 31 days (May 31) 3 rd cut-off: 19 Jun – 16 Jul '23
Notification Results	31 July '22	1 st cut-off: Jan '23 2 nd cut-off: Mar '23	1 st cut-off: Jun '23 2 nd cut-off: Jul '23 3 rd cut-off: Aug '23
TA suggested period	Sept – Dec '22	Mar – Jun '23	Sept '23 – Jan '24

Table 1 Structure of the Open Calls for Transnational Access

4.1 Mitigation strategies

Considering the low number of applications received in the 1st Open Call, the VITALISE Consortium designed and implemented some specific mitigation strategies to cope with a potential low rate of applications in the following Open Calls. Herein, a summary is provided of the measures adopted all throughout the 2nd and 3rd Open Call to increase the number of submissions.

4.1.1 2nd Open Call

As mitigation strategies in the 2nd Open Call, the following actions have been performed:

- Included as eligible applicants also master's students;
- Shortened the "Application Template" for describing the research project in order to make the submission process more usable and user friendly;
- Anticipated and enlarged the Open Call submission period (also for the 3rd Open Call);
- Divided the submission period in 2 cut-offs (also for the 3rd Open Call);
- Improved the information available on the project website and created dedicated informational material (in collaboration with WP13);
- Defined an individual recruitment strategy (in collaboration with WP13).

4.1.2 3rd Open Call

For the 3rd Open Call, enhancements were made to the informational material and refinements were implemented in shaping the individual recruitment strategy. As a result of a direct discussion with the PO, the eligibility criteria were further expanded to broaden the potential applicant pool; in reviewing the eligibility criteria, specific measures were also taken to keep ensuring scientific excellence. Undergraduate students were allowed to perform TA as research team members, under the direct supervision of the leading applicant (either a professor or post-doc affiliated to university or research centre). Also, research teams were allowed to apply for more than one LL to conduct a comparative study by submitting more than one complementary application.

In order to encourage applications to LLs that did not receive many applications in the frame of the 1st and 2nd Open Call, some infographics were added both on the website and on the application toolkit, that displayed each LL capacity to host researchers. The infographic was regularly updated during the 3 cut-offs. Additionally, as an additional mitigation strategy, it was introduced the possibility for researchers affiliated to partner organizations but not directly engaged in the VITALISE project to apply to TA.

In the frame of the 3rd Open Call, the Individual recruitment strategy was utterly strengthened. The VITALISE partnership was encouraged to disseminate the 3rd Open Call among their professional network. In order to give the Living Labs more time to work on this individual recruitment strategy, the 2nd cut-off was extended to May 31st. This deadline extension brought to the definitive achievement of the KPI1.1 Number of total researchers recruited for trans-national access: >100 researchers: with the closure of the 2nd cut-off of the 3rd Open Call, in fact, 112 researchers in total were recruited.

As additional mitigation strategy, researchers internal to the VITALISE consortium were also encouraged to submit application, under the condition that they were not actively working on the VITALISE project. It must be noted that this mitigation strategy has not been applied but in one case.

As the Living Lab capacity was strongly reduced for the 2nd cut-off, it was introduced the “first come-first served” basis as evaluation criterion: the first applications submitted were also the first ones to undergo the evaluation procedure. This measure was taken to incentivize the applicants to submit in shorter time their proposals in order to secure the availability of their preferred Living Lab.

Despite having reached the KPI1.1 at the closure of the 2nd cut-off of the 3rd OC, some Living Labs (UPM and INTRAS) still had to reach the envisaged number of visiting researchers. The final mitigation strategy to ensure that all the Living Labs could reach their envisaged KPI, was to open a 3rd cut-off exclusively dedicated to UPM and INTRAS. This cut-off was run between June 16th and July 19th 2023. During this 3rd cut-off, 1 additional researcher was recruited, finally reaching 113 external researchers.

4.2 Results of the 1st Open Call for Transnational Access

For the 1st Open Call, 6 proposals were submitted, 4 of which were approved, for a total of 11 researchers conducting the TA (7 females and 4 males). The following Table summarizes the main features of the submitted proposals.

Project ID	No. of applicants	Gender	Working country	Domain	Selected Living Lab
ID9	5	5F	Albania	Academia	AUTH Healthcare Transitions Living Lab
ID10	1	1F	Greece	Academia	Rejected: not feasible
ID11	1	1M	Costa Rica	Academia	Rejected: not eligible
ID12	1	1F	Bosnia and Herzegovina	Academia	AIT Technology Experience Laboratory
ID13	4	3M, 1F	Slovenia	Academia	Intras VR/AR and Snoezelen Room
ID14	1	1M	Hungary	Academia	McGill – CRIR rehabilitation Living Lab

Table 2 Results of the 1st Open Call for Transnational Access

4.3 Results of the 2nd Open Call for Transnational Access

As previously explained, the 2nd Open Call was divided into 2 cut-offs. In the 1st cut-off 7 applications were submitted and 6 of them were approved, for a total of 10 researchers. During the 2nd cut-off, a total of 16 applications were received and approved, resulting in the recruitment of an additional 31 researchers for Transnational Access.

Project ID	No. of applicants	Gender	Working country	Domain	Selected Living Lab
ID 19	1	1M	Italy	Academia	Rejected: non eligible
ID20	1	1F	Norway	Academia	LiCalab Older Adults' Homes
ID21	1	1M	UK	Academia	AUTH Healthcare Transitions Living Lab
ID22	1	1F	Germany	Academia	McGill – CRIR rehabilitation Living Lab
ID23*	4	3M, 1F	Slovenia	Academia	AUTH Centrifuge rehabilitation Living Lab
ID24	1	1F	Italy	Governmental Researcher	AIT Technology Experience Laboratory
ID25	2	2F	Greece	Academia	McGill – CRIR rehabilitation Living Lab

Table 3 Results of the 1st cut-off of the 2nd Open Call for Transnational Access

*The projects ID23 and ID13 are partially composed by the same team, as the leading applicant and another researcher in ID13 have also participated in ID23. These researchers were just counted once in the total recruited researchers' headcount.

Project ID	No. of applicants	Gender	Working country	Domain	Selected Living Lab
ID27	1	1M	Spain	Academia	Nagykovácsi Wellbeing Living Lab - Trebag
ID28	1	1M	Italy	Academia	AUTH Living environment simulation
ID29	1	1F	Austria	Academia	McGill – CRIR rehabilitation Living Lab
ID30	2	1M, 1F	Cyprus	Academia	Nagykovácsi Wellbeing Living Lab - Trebag
ID31	2	2F	Romania	Academia	AUTH Living environment simulation
ID33	1	1M	Italy	Academia	Laurea Simulated Hospital

ID34	3	1M, 2F	Italy	Academia	AUTH Living environment simulation
ID35	2	1M, 1F	UK	Academia	AUTH Healthcare Transitions Living Lab
ID36	4	4M	Romania	Academia	Thomas More LiCalab Experience Lab
ID40	3	1M, 2F	France	Academia	Laurea Activity Living Lab
ID41	2	1M, 1F	Spain	Academia	Laurea Activity Living Lab
ID42	1	1F	Argentina	Academia	Intras Rehabilitation
ID43	2	2M	Bulgaria	Entrepreneur	Thomas More LiCalab Experience Lab
ID44*	2	2F	Germany	Academia	McGill – CRIR rehabilitation Living Lab
ID45	1	1M	Netherlands	Academia	Laurea Activity Living Lab
ID48	3	2M, 1F	Belgium	Industrial Researchers	McGill – CRIR rehabilitation Living Lab

Table 4 Results of the 2nd cut-off of the 2nd Open Call for Transnational Access

*The projects ID44 and ID22 are partially composed by the same team, as the leading applicant in ID22 has also participated in ID44. This researcher was just counted once in the total recruited researchers' headcount.

4.4 3rd Open Call for Transnational Access

The 3rd Open Call was structured into 3 cut-offs. In the 1st cut-off 9 applications were received: they were all approved for a total of 13 additional recruited researchers. During the 2nd cut-off, 18 applications were received, for a total of 50 additional recruited researchers. In the 3rd cut off (exclusively dedicated to INTRAS and UPM), only 2 applications were submitted, resulting in 1 additional recruited researcher.

Project ID	No. of applicants	Gender	Working country	Domain	Selected Living Lab
ID51	2	2F	UK	Entrepreneur	Laurea Simulated Hospital
ID56	1	1M	Greece	Industrial Researcher	LiCalab Older Adults' Homes
ID57	2	2F	Ireland	Academia	Thomas More gaitlab – Mobilab
ID58*	3	3F	Ireland	Living Lab Practitioner	LiCalab Older Adults' Homes

ID59	2	2F	UK	Academia	UPM-LifeSTech- The Smart House Living Lab
ID60	1	1F	France	Entrepreneur	LiCalab Older Adults' Homes
ID61	1	1F	Switzerland	Academia	Thomas More LiCalab Experience Lab
ID69**	2	2M	Israel	Industrial Researcher	Ozean Living Lab
ID70**	2	2M	Israel	Industrial Researcher	GAIA Smart Spaces

Table 5 Results of the 1st cut-off of the 3rd Open Call for Transnational Access

*The projects ID58 and ID57 are partially composed by the same team, as the leading applicant and another researcher in ID57 have also participated in ID58. These researchers were just counted once in the total recruited researchers' headcount.

**Projects ID69 and ID70 are composed by the same research team. These researchers were counted just once in the overall recruited researcher's headcount.

Project ID	No. of applicants	Gender	Working country	Domain	Selected Living Lab
ID71	5	5M	UK	Academia	Laurea Activity Living Lab
ID72	5	5M	UK	Academia	LiCalab Older Adults' Homes
ID73	2	2F	Portugal	Entrepreneur	GAIA Smart Spaces
ID75	1	1F	UK	Academia	Licalab Older Adult's Home
ID76	4	4F	Albania	Academia	GAIA Smart Spaces
ID82	3	3F	UK	Academia	INTRAS MIND lab for AHA & Independent Living
ID83	5	2M, 3F	UK	Academia	AIT Technology Experience Laboratory
ID84	1	1F	Ireland	Academia	Ozean Living Lab
ID85	2	1M, 1F	Poland	Academia	Nagykovácsi Wellbeing Living Lab - Trebag
ID86*	3	3F	France	Academia	INTRAS MIND lab for AHA & Independent Living
ID90	1	1F	Romania	Academia	AIT Technology Experience Laboratory

ID91	1	1M	Portugal	Academia	Nagykovácsi Wellbeing Living Lab
ID92	5	1M, 4F	Argentina	Academia	INTRAS VR/AR and Snoezelen Room
ID93	4	3M, 1F	Poland	Academia	UPM-LifeSTech- The Smart House Living Lab
ID94	2	1M, 1F	Portugal	Government Researcher	INTRAS MIND lab for AHA & Independent Living
ID95	5	2M, 3F	Netherlands	Academia	AUTH Centrifuge rehabilitation Living Lab
ID96**	1	1F	Italy	Government Researcher	GAIA Smart Spaces
ID97	2	1M, 1F	Hungary	Academia	Ozean Living Lab

Table 6 Results of the 2nd cut-off of the 3rd Open Call for Transnational Access

*The projects ID86 and ID82 are partially composed by the same team, as the leading applicant in ID82 has also participated in ID86. This researcher was just counted once in the total recruited researchers' headcount.

**This researcher also participated in the frame of the 2nd Open Call (Project ID24). This researcher was counted just once in the overall recruited researcher's headcount.

Project ID	No. of applicants	Gender	Working country	Domain	Selected Living Lab
ID98	1	1F	Colombia	Other	INTRAS Rehabilitation Living Lab
ID99	1	1M	Italy	Industrial Researcher	Rejected: not feasible

Table 7 Results of the 3rd cut-off of the 3rd Open Call for Transnational Access

Despite being opened for UPM and INTRAS research infrastructures, the 3rd Open Call recruited just one researcher for INTRAS. While the 3rd cut-off was running in fact, the lead applicant of project ID59 formally added as a member of the research team an additional person, thus ensuring UPM the reaching of its KPI. The researcher CV was also mentioned in the Application template in the Team section.

4.5 Final Results of the Open Calls for Transnational Access

The following figures offer insights related to the selected applications of the 3 Open Calls for Transnational Access. Table 8 details the three Open Calls in terms of applications submitted and selected with the corresponding number of researchers admitted to TA. As it can be seen, out of 58 received applications, 54 were approved. This process resulted in having 122 researchers selected. However, as far as the KPI1.1 is concerned, only 113 researchers can be counted since 9 of them were involved in more than one proposal, and they were selected to conduct TA in 2 different LLs.

Open Calls	N. of applications submitted	No. of selected applications	Total selected researchers
1 st Open Call	6	4	11
2 nd Open Call	23	22	38 (41*)
3 rd Open Call	29	28	64 (70*)
Total	58	54	113 (122*)

Table 8 Number of selected applications and researchers

*The total researchers are presented in terms of both the number accountable for the KPI1.1 achievement and, in parenthesis, the total number of researchers admitted to TA.

The number of applications submitted has increased significantly through the 3 Open Calls, therefore it can be stated that the mitigation strategies (described in par. 4.1) that have been implemented between the 1st and the 2nd Open call and again between the 2nd and the 3rd have brought significant improvements in fulfilling the KPI. As such, 11% of the KPI1.1 was reached with the 1st Open Call, 49% with the 2nd, and with the 3rd Open Call KPI was exceeded by reaching a total of 113 selected researchers.

Figure 8 shows the distributions of the selected researchers across the 9 LLs. As can be clearly observed from the graph, at the end of the evaluation process, all LLs have reached the number of expected researchers.

Figure 8 Selected Researchers and expected researchers per each LL

Figure 9 shows the distribution of proposals by team size: most proposals involved teams of 1 or 2 members (37 accepted applications out of 54), with fewer proposals with 3, 4 or 5 team members.

Figure 9 Number of teams per team members

Regarding the average score of the scientific evaluation (Fig. 10), the 2nd and 3rd Open Calls displayed higher average scientific scores, with values of 69.2 and 69.1 out of 100, respectively, while the 1st Open Call presented a lower average score of 52.5.

Figure 10 Average scientific score per Open Call

Figure 11 shows the gender distribution among selected applicants, showing a higher female participation (64 female vs 49 male).

Figure 11 Gender distribution of selected applicants

The working domain of the applicants varied throughout the three Open Calls (Fig. 12). Indeed, for the 1st Open Call, all the received applications solely originated from the academic domain. Subsequently, in the 2nd and 3rd Open Calls, the proportion of academic applications increasingly

reduced indicating a diversification of application domains. This transition highlights a notable change in the composition of applications, emphasizing the evolution from an exclusively academic focus in the 1st Open Call to a more diversified range of domains in the subsequent calls. This was the result of mitigation strategies applied by the consortium to promote VITALISE research among industrial researchers, especially in response to recommendations from the first review. Just to mention a few, partner AV intensively promoted the VITALISE Open Calls in entrepreneurship trainings.

The final percentages showed in Figure 13 illustrate a predominance of academic applications, comprising 72% of the total, followed by industrial researcher applications at 13%. Entrepreneurial and government researcher categories represent 7% and 6% of the total applications, respectively, while the Living Lab practitioner category, though in smaller representation, contributed 2% to the total applications. These data underscore a diversification in the domains of received applications, highlighting the growing interest from various professional areas and research sectors, contributing to the overall richness and diversity of the applicant pool across the three Open Calls.

Figure 12 Working domain of selected applicants through the 3 Open Calls

Figure 13 Working domain of selected applicants

As can be seen from Figure 14, the 3 Open Calls reached a very broad audience, with selected candidates working in several countries. Overall, the selected researchers come from 24 different

states, with a particularly large number of applicants from UK (9), followed by Italy (4), France, Ireland, Romania, Portugal, and Slovenia (3).

Figure 14 Working country of selected applicants

Regarding the nationality of origin of single researchers, again there is a high number of researchers with British nationality (10), followed by Italian nationality (9), Irish and Albanian (8), and French and Romanian (7) (Fig. 15).

Figure 15 Geographical distribution of nationalities of selected applicants

Summarizing, the strategic goal of selecting 100 researchers was successfully met, contributing to a diverse pool of participants from different working domains and geographical origins. The analysis highlights the international nature of the initiative, underlining the significance of geographical diversity in achieving a successful and impactful research collaboration.

5 TA management

In order to properly report the activities and costs related to each TA project, the TAM, in strict collaboration with all WP11 partners, coordinated the design of bespoke procedure to: 1) Provide external researchers with complete information on the Research Infrastructure and Transnational Access; 2) Produce complete documentation of the activities; 3) Collect feedbacks on the services provided during TA.

This procedure was firstly drafted at M24 (Mar '23) and presented during the 2nd plenary meeting in Vienna to the whole partnership. It was successively integrated according to specific needs expressed by the Living Lab and by the Project Coordinator.

The management of TA was carried out autonomously by each Living Lab with the support of the TAM. The TA reporting procedure can be divided into 3 main sections:

- Activities to be completed before the TA period;
- Activities to carry out during TA period;
- Activities to complete after the conclusion of TA period.

During the whole deployment of TA, the TAM provided constant remote support to the LLs in the implementation of TA activities. Details about the actual implementation of TA activities will be provided by WP8-9-10 in their final report at M36. In the following paragraphs the TA reporting procedure and TA monitoring activities will be widely described.

Activities to be completed before the TA period

- Infopack Introduction: Initiate communication with External Researchers by providing the Infopack, offering a comprehensive overview of required documentation and tasks before, during, and after TA;
- Contract Agreement (CA): Download and customize the CA for TA, integrating the agreement number and applicant details. After discussing it with the applicant, merge it with the application form, and share it with the applicant for the legal representative's signature;
- Bilateral Contract Agreement (if applicable): If necessary, collaborate on a bilateral contract agreement with the researcher, ensuring confidentiality;
- EU Survey Access for Questionnaires: Grant access to the EU Survey platform for sharing questionnaires, following the Quick Guide;
- Expectations Questionnaire Dissemination: Share the Expectations Questionnaire through EU Survey, ensuring completion before TA initiation;
- Training and Preparation: Conduct the Fast Track Training Programme (FTTP) for researchers accessing the infrastructure, promoting optional use of NoteTheBook;
- Amendments Handling: Facilitate any changes to the research team by providing a CA addendum and updating relevant documentation;
- Declaration for TA Cancellation (if applicable): In case of TA withdrawal, fill and sign the Declaration of TA Cancellation.

Activities to be carried out during TA period

- Research Log Management: Prompt researchers to daily update the Research Log through EUSurvey, with new weekly links;
- Receipts Collection Reminder: Remind researchers to gather and keep all receipts during their TA period;
- Track LLs effort: Regularly track the efforts of your team in organizing and managing TA.

Activities to be completed after the conclusion of TA period

- TA Evaluation: Share TA evaluation questionnaires through EU Survey, encouraging timely completion;
- Final Report Submission: Share the template "Report for TA" for reporting the TA activities, request completion, and upload the document to Teams for comprehensive project documentation;
- Exploitation Potential Assessment: Disseminate the two questionnaires evaluating the exploitation potential;
- Reimbursement Coordination: Guide applicants on the reimbursement process, emphasizing the submission of all required documents;
- Data Anonymization Verification: Confirm if the research team declared data anonymization in the Final Report TA for compliance.

6 TA monitoring activities

The deployment in TA activities started on M23 (Feb '23): the first TA project took place in AUTH Healthcare Transitions Living Lab. In order to ensure the smooth running of all TA and the complete production of the documentation previously described, the TAM constantly assisted the LLs in the implementation of the TA management procedure. This mainly happened in 5 different modes:

- Training on TA management procedure: During the 2nd Plenary Meeting in Vienna, the TAM presented to the LLs the entire management procedure, duly describing the documentation to be produced and referring to the correct templates to be applied;
- Monitoring of the advancement of the documentation: The TAM coordinated an internal procedure to periodically monitor the production of the needed document for the implementation of the TA. To do so, the TAM was constantly in touch with the appointed responsible of each LL to support them in keeping track of the TA implementation;
- Email exchange: The LLs were always able to contact by email the TAM in case of specific needs. Upon request, the TAM was also available for bilateral meetings to clarify any aspect of the procedure and, whenever was needed, the Project Coordinator was being involved;
- Training on the TA monitoring file: The TA monitoring file was designed by the TAM in close collaboration with the Project Coordinator in order to monitor the economic and time effort of the LLs on each TA project. This is paramount to the scope of determining the costs of an operating Living Lab. The file was then introduced as part of the TA Management procedure in July 2023. The TAM held two consecutive meetings with the LLs to present the file, and train the TA reference persons on their correct use, while also collecting feedbacks on the usability of the file;
- Bilateral TA monitoring meetings: In order to assess the advancement of the TA documentation and to clarify any doubt that might have occurred since the beginning of TA deployment, the TAM set face-to-face calls with the LLs at M30.

The TAM held weekly telcos to manage and implement WP11 activities in close collaboration with the project coordinator and the partners involved in WP11. The main focus of these telcos was the smooth running of the Open Calls for Transnational Access, the design of the Materials for the Open Calls (see D11.1). These telcos were also dedicated to the design of the TA Management procedure and to the discussion of particular situations occurred to LLs participating during TA activities implementation. Details about the actual monitoring activities of TA will be provided by WP8-9-10 in their final report at M36.

As the TA deployment unfolded in fact, LLs faced some unexpected situations, such as changes in the approved TA project, specific requests by external researchers and TA cancellations. The TAM, in close collaboration with all the partners involved in WP11, worked to adapt the TA management procedure in order to provide support to LLs in all these situations. This brought to the development of bespoke templates to support LLs in the task of correctly reporting variations to the approved TA projects and responding to the requests of external researchers with appropriate tools. In particular, the following materials and template were produced:

- Infopack for Researchers, listing all the documents that had to be produced during TA by researchers (Appendix 10);
- Certificate of Attendance to TA and FTTP (Appendix 11);
- Declaration for TA cancellation (Appendix 12);
- Addendum to the Contract Agreement for Transnational Access, with the scope of reporting amendments to the research team (Appendix 13).

7 Application procedure for Virtual Access

The application procedure for VA was designed to be streamlined and time-saving. Unlike TA, individuals submitting applications for accessing the VITALISE Discovery Portal to have VA to the available datasets, are not required to undergo an assessment process, as they will only have to meet the following eligibility criteria that will be self-reported:

- I work in an institution established in a Member State of the European Union or in a state associated to the H2020 Programme (Not sure? Check the List of countries eligible for funding in this [link](#));
- At least 80% of my research team members works in a Member State of the European Union or in a state associated to the H2020 Programme;
- Neither me nor any of my team members have Russian or Belarusian origin;
- I am willing to comply with the obligation to disseminate the results, acknowledging the source of the data (For more information regarding the valorisation procedure, please advise par. 8 of the [Application Manual](#));
- The User Group Leader/Supervisor holds an academic title of at least Master Degree level;
- If my research team also includes undergraduate/bachelor students, the leading applicant is a professor or postdoc affiliated to a University or Research Centre.

The applicants will have to confirm their compliance to the listed eligibility criteria, assuming responsibility for truthfulness, and as no feasibility and scientific evaluation is required, after completing the submission they will be able to access the Discovery Portal.

Preliminary information about the access to the Discovery Portal have been made available in D11.1. Materials for Open Calls. Subsequently, in strict collaboration with WP13, the Application Manual for TA and VA V4.1 was updated and published on the VITALISE website (see Appendix 14 for the latest updates about VA). Moreover, always in close cooperation with WP13, the website has been and will be constantly updated with the latest information pertaining to the deployment of the VA.

8 Conclusions

This deliverable has provided a detailed overview of the design of the evaluation procedure of the Open Calls for Transnational Access (TA) all the data about the received and the accepted proposals and the information about the design of the application procedure for VA. Regarding the TA, the KPI1.1 “Number of total researchers recruited for transnational access: >100 researchers” was successfully met as 113 researchers for TA were recruited. The 3 Open Calls attracted a wide audience, with candidates applying from more than 20 countries. The selected applications came from different professional fields and research areas, showing increased interest from diverse sectors throughout the 3 Open Calls. At the time of submission of this deliverable, the TA in its deployment phase and the TAM, working in close collaboration with all the WP11 partners, is actively supporting all the LLs in the implementation of the TA management and monitoring procedures. At the time of submission of this deliverable, the data to evaluate the achievement of KPI1.2 “Number of total researchers recruited for virtual access: >200 researchers” are not available as the VA has not been launched yet.

Appendices

Appendix 1 – Template eligibility evaluation

VITALISE Project's 3rd Open Call – 2nd cut off for TA Eligibility Evaluation and priorities check

NAME OF THE EVALUATOR	XXX
PARTNER	XXX
NAME OF THE APPLICANT	XXX XXX

Eligibility check

Please evaluate the application based on the following eligibility criteria.

Eligibility Criteria	Yes or No
They should work in an institution established in a Member State of the European Union or in a state associated to H2020 Programme. Researchers working in other countries can apply but they cannot represent more than 20% of the total number of researchers (unit of access?) that will access the VITALISE facilities. If not EU or Associated, report here the Country: ...	
They cannot have Russian or Belarusian origin.	
They must work in a country other than the country where the infrastructure is based, as the Access is "Transnational". If the researchers work in a country where one of the Living Labs is located, the researchers will not have access to this specific Living Lab.	
They must disseminate the results and knowledge they will generate during the access to the Living Lab, unless it goes against the legitimate interest of their organization. If not possible, report a summary of the reason why ...	
They must hold a master's degree or if the leading applicant is a master's student, at least 1 member of the team must hold a master's degree and act as supervisor of the TA (he/she/they could join the TA fully remote)	
Master the English language (check if the abstract is well written and clear)	
ELIGIBLE	

Priorities check

Please check if the application meets the following priority criteria.

Priority Criterion – Open Access	Yes or No
The applicants ensure scientific excellence and fully embrace Open Access policies.	
If not, explain why	
...	
Total (0-1)	

Priority Criteria per infrastructure - INFRASTRUCTURE 1	Yes or No
Name of the Infrastructure XXX	
The applicants have not previously used the infrastructure	
The applicants are working in countries where no equivalent research infrastructure exists	
Number of priority criteria (from 0 to 2)	

Priority Criteria per infrastructure - INFRASTRUCTURE 2	Yes or No
Name of the Infrastructure XXX	
The applicants have not previously used the infrastructure	
The applicants are working in countries where no equivalent research infrastructure exists	
Number of priority criteria (from 0 to 2)	

Priority Criteria per infrastructure - INFRASTRUCTURE 3	Yes or No
Name of the Infrastructure XXX	
The applicants have not previously used the infrastructure	
The applicants are working in countries where no equivalent research infrastructure exists	
Number of priority criteria (from 0 to 2)	

Reallocation

Is the applicant interested in being reallocated, if needed?

Yes/No

Comments

Please provide a brief comment for the applicant in case the application is not eligible.

I declare that there is no conflict of interest regarding the evaluation of this application.

DATE OF EVALUATION

SIGNATURE

Appendix 2 – Template feasibility evaluation

VITALISE Project's 3rd Open Call – 2nd cut off for TA Feasibility Evaluation

NAME OF THE EVALUATOR	XXX
PARTNER	XXX
NAME OF THE APPLICANT	XXX
ID OF THE APPLICATION	XXX
INFRASTRUCTURE CHOSEN	XXX

Feasibility check

Please evaluate the application based on the following feasibility criteria.

Feasibility Criteria	Yes or No
Can the Living Lab Research Infrastructure provide the required access?	
If not feasible, briefly explain why ...	
Can the Living Lab Research Infrastructure provide the required services?	
If not feasible, briefly explain why ...	
Can the Living Lab Research Infrastructure support the study in terms of end-user's recruitment?	
If not feasible, briefly explain why ...	
FEASIBLE	

Applicant declarations check

Please provide the following information.

Questions	Yes or No
To the best of your knowledge, have the applicants previously used the infrastructure?	
Do the applicants work in countries where, as long as you know, no equivalent research infrastructure exists? Yes: the applicants work in countries where no equivalent research infrastructure exists. No: they work in a country where there is a similar infrastructure. If not, please write the name of the similar infrastructure: ...	
Do the applicants ensure scientific excellence and fully embrace Open Access policies? If not, explain why ...	

Application not feasible

Please provide a brief comment for the applicant in case the application is not feasible. If possible, provide some suggestions to improve the application for resubmission.

Comment (optional)

Please write here any comment about the application, if needed

I declare that there is no conflict of interest regarding the evaluation of this application.

DATE OF EVALUATION

SIGNATURE

Appendix 3 – Template Scientific evaluation

VITALISE Project's 3rd Open Call for TA – 2nd cut off Scientific Evaluation

NAME OF THE EVALUATOR	XXX
ID OF THE APPLICATION	XXX
NAME OF THE APPLICATION LEADER (1 st applicant on the report)	XXX XXX

Scientific Evaluation

Please evaluate the application based on a scale from 1 to 10, according to the guide below.

Score	
1-2	Poor. The criterion is inadequately addressed or there are serious inherent weaknesses.
3-4	Fair. The proposal broadly addresses the criterion, but there are significant weaknesses
5-6	Good. The proposal addresses the criterion well, but a number of shortcomings are present.
7-8	Very good. The proposal addresses the criterion very well, but a small number of shortcomings are present.
9-10	Excellent. The proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion. Any shortcomings are minor.

Scientific Criteria	Score 1-10
<p>Scientific and technical quality of the proposal Is the current <i>state of knowledge</i> in the research area well described? Are <i>cited references</i> relevant and reflect the state-of-the-art? Is the proposed topic of <i>high scientific quality</i> and does it provide innovative aspects? Are the <i>research objectives</i> and expected deliverables/outputs of the proposal clearly stated? Are they <i>achievable</i>? To which extent do the expected results <i>lead to a progress beyond the current state-of-the-art</i>? Is a clear concept presented on how the gathered <i>data will be collected, shared, analysed and published</i>?</p>	
<p>Quality of the work plan Is the work plan <i>adequate</i>? Is it <i>clearly described</i> and well defined? Can the proposed work plan <i>be realized</i> in the set time? Are the scheduled tasks and methods <i>adequate to the set objectives</i>? Is it clearly stated which <i>methods and equipment</i> will be employed? Does the proposed project <i>maximise the use of the infrastructure</i>? Has the proposal <i>assessed any likely risks</i>?</p>	
<p>Scientific qualification/track record of the proposing PI and user group Background/<i>track record of the PI</i>, Background/<i>track record of the scientific team</i>, Are the <i>roles and responsibilities of the scientific team</i> clearly stated? Is the <i>combined expertise</i> suitable to achieve the research objective?</p>	
<p>Innovation What currently unmet need/s do the innovative aspect/s address, and for whom? How do they differ from existing tools or practices? Does the proposal present a significant departure from current practice? Can the proposal provide a demonstrable improvement (time, resources, cost, effectiveness) over current methods/tools? Are the results (tools or practices) suitable for commercialization and exploitation outside the context of a research environment? Can the proposal lead to the development of a substantially new product or service?</p>	
<p>Collaboration with international/national partners/industry To what extent are <i>new European user groups with limited access to living labs infrastructure</i> integrated? To what extent is the proposed project <i>embedded into larger research programmes on a national, EU or international level</i>? What is the <i>potential for a long-term integration/collaboration on an international level</i>? Are <i>collaborations with industry envisaged</i>?</p>	
<p>Training of young scientists/public outreach How many <i>young scientists and students at PhD level and below</i> will be involved? Are there <i>dissemination activities</i>, addressing the general public, planned?</p>	

Comment

Please provide a brief comment about the evaluation.

I declare that there is no conflict of interest regarding the evaluation of this application.

DATE OF EVALUATION

SIGNATURE

Appendix 4 – Template notification accepted proposal for TA

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101007990.

VITALISE project
Horizon 2020
Project Coordinator
Evdokimos I. Konstantinidis
EnoLL – European Network
of Living Labs

Subject: VITALISE project
3rd Open Call for Transnational Access to the Living Labs

Dear Madam/Sir,

We are writing in connection with your application for the above-mentioned call.

Having evaluated your application based on the project description and the information provided in the online application toolkit, we are glad to inform you that you have been selected for Transnational Access to the Living Labs at the following infrastructure:

XXX

In the next few weeks, you will be contacted by the Research Infrastructure Leader to organize the Transnational Access to the infrastructure.

We thank you for your interest in VITALISE.

Yours faithfully,

Evdokimos I. Konstantinidis

Appendix 5 – Template notification rejected proposal for TA

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101007990.

VITALISE project
Horizon 2020
Project Coordinator
Evdokimos I. Konstantinidis
EnoLL – European Network
of Living Labs
Avenue des Arts 6
1210 Brussels, Belgium

Subject: VITALISE project
2nd Open Call for Transnational Access to the Living Labs – 1st cut-off

Dear Madam/Sir,

We are writing in connection with your proposal for the above-mentioned call.

Having evaluated your application based on the project description and the information provided in the online application toolkit, we regret to inform you that your application for Transnational Access to the Living Labs has been rejected.

Please find below the evaluation of your project.

...

Based on the received review, we invite you to improve your application and re-submit it to the 3rd Open Call that will be opened between March and April 2023 and will allow Transnational Access approximately between September 2023 and January 2024.

We thank you for your interest in VITALISE.

Yours faithfully,

Evdokimos I. Konstantinidis

Copyright message: ©VITALISE Consortium, 2021.

<https://vitalise-project.eu>

Appendix 6 – Template for the evaluation of the applicants for the External Evaluators

VITALISE Project's Evaluation template for external research proposal evaluators

NAME OF THE EVALUATOR	
PARTNER	

NAME OF THE APPLICANT	
DATE OF APPLICATION	

Evaluation

Please evaluate the application on a scale from 0 to 2, where 0 means “without experience” and 2 means “experienced”, how experienced is the applicants on the following domains and calculate the final score.

Experience	From 0 to 2
in the Health & Wellbeing domain (e.g., Degree, working experience)	
in the Living Lab methodology (e.g., specific publications, nr. years working in a LL)	
research experience (e.g., publications, projects)	
in technology and innovation (e.g., projects, working experience, degree, nr. of product or services developed)	
in academic achievement with relevant publications (e.g., positions, publications, nr. of grants or funding)	
as an evaluator (e.g., nr. of time being an evaluator or a reviewer, coherence with the topic)	
motivational letter	
FINAL SCORE	

Comments

Please provide a brief comment to the final score:

- If the final score is between 0 and 7, write a brief comment to the applicant explaining why his/her application was considered not eligible for the role of external research proposal evaluator (suggested length between 500 and 1.000 characters)
- If the final score is between 8 and 9, write a brief comment to discuss the application with the full board

FINAL SCORE	RESULT	COMMENT
0-7	Not accepted	
8-9	To be discussed by the full board	
10-14	Accepted	<i>No comment needed</i>

I declare that there is no conflict of interest regarding the evaluation of this application.

DATE OF EVALUATION

SIGNATURE

Appendix 7 – Template notification evaluation procedure candidate External Evaluator

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101007990.

VITALISE project
Horizon 2020
Project Coordinator
EnoLL – European Network
of Living Labs
Avenue des Arts 6
1210 Brussels, Belgium

Subject: VITALISE project
Call for external research proposal evaluators

Dear Madam/Sir,

We are writing in connection with your application for the above-mentioned call.

Having evaluated your application based on your CV and motivational letter, we are glad to inform you that you have been selected as an external research proposal evaluator for the VITALISE Open Calls.

Thus, you are now officially part of the list of the external research proposal evaluators and you will be asked to scientifically evaluate the proposals received over the 3 VITALISE Open Calls, based on your availability.

As a first step, we kindly ask you to reply to the email formally stating your availability to evaluate the applications of the 1st VITALISE Open Call between June and July 2022.

In the next few weeks, we will provide more details about how to conduct the evaluations.

We thank you for your interest in VITALISE.

Yours faithfully,

VITALISE Team

Appendix 8 – Contract Agreement for External Evaluators

?????

European
Network of
Living Labs

EXTERNAL EVALUATOR CONTRACT

This service contract (hereinafter referred to as the “Contract”) has been established by and between:

European Network of Living Labs iVZW, hereinafter referred to as “ENoLL”. Registered office at Kunstlaan 6, 1210 Sint-Joost-ten-Node, Brussels, Belgium, registered under number 0824.793.473, and hereby duly represented by Evdokimos Konstantinidis, Chairman of the Executive Board of ENoLL.

And,

Name and Surname hereinafter referred to as “External Evaluator”, with domicile in XXXX, VAT number XXXX.

Hereinafter separately referred to as “Party” and collectively as “Parties”

The Parties agree as follows:

Article 1

For the purpose of providing support in the execution of the VITALISE Project, Grant Agreement: 101007990, where ENoLL is involved as Coordinator, in the context of the applications evaluations of the VITALISE LLs within WP11, the External Evaluator shall provide services to the satisfactory fulfilment of the tasks described in Article 2.

The assignment will be executed during the period from July 2022 until August 2022. The exact timetable and time allocated to ENoLL can vary according to the *ad hoc* needs, and tasks revisions in light of progress or other circumstances.

Article 2

The assignment mentioned in article 1 shall consist of the following tasks:

The External Expert will have to perform the scientific evaluation of the application received in the 1st Open Call of the VITALISE project. To conduct the evaluation the External Expert will receive 3 (three) documents:

- The report of the application containing the information about the applicants, the infrastructures they prefer to access, the list of services needed and the abstract of the project they want to perform, hereinafter referred to as “Report of the application”;
- The “Application Template for Transnational Access to the Research Infrastructures of VITALISE Project” with the project description, hereinafter referred to as “Project description”;

European Network of Living Labs iVZW – mailing address: Kunstlaan 6, 1210 Sint-Joost-ten-Node, Brussels, Belgium
info@enoll.org - Legal Registry. N°: BE 0824 793 473

?

1

- The template “VITALISE Project’s 1st Open Call for TA – Scientific Evaluation”, hereinafter referred to as “Template for Scientific Evaluation”.

The External Expert will evaluate the application, on the basis of the Report of the Application and the Project description. The evaluation will be performed according to the provided Template for Scientific Evaluation: this includes 6 evaluation criteria, (to be valued on a scale from 1 to 10, accordingly to the guide provided), plus a brief comment about the evaluation.

Having filled out the Template for Scientific Evaluation in all its part, the External Expert will sign it, transform the file in a .pdf and send it to the Transnational Access Manager – TAM (Social IT) within 15 days after receiving the above-mentioned documents.

The content of the above-described tasks can be altered in mutual agreement between the parties. The External Expert commits to regularly update ENoLL on the progress of the agreed upon tasks.

Article 3

For the purpose of these activities, the External Expert will adhere to all internal organisation policies that are applicable within ENoLL. This includes:

- The External Expert will work under the instructions of the beneficiary (i.e., the work is decided, designed and supervised by ENoLL);
- For the execution of the appointed tasks, and following the international nature of these tasks, it is agreed that the External Expert can perform these on a teleworking basis;
- The External Expert commits to keep all records and supporting documentation for two years starting from the date of the last payment. This documentation will be provided to ENoLL if there are on-going checks, audits, investigations, appeals, litigation or pursuit of claims, and be available throughout the duration of these procedures;

Article 4

The External Expert agrees to invoice ENoLL after the successful completion of agreed deliverables at the end of the assignment end of August 2022.

The maximum billable for the overall completion of the contract may not exceed the value of 30,00 € euros, excluding VAT if applicable.

If for tax purposes the External Expert is based outside of Belgium but within the European Union or a country where similar conditions apply, the Consultant shall issue invoices without charging local VAT but with the Belgian VAT registration number of ENoLL (BE 0824.793.473). The invoice must reflect this reverse VAT status by including the phrase: “VAT exempt -art. 44 of EU Council Directive 2006/112/EC of 28 November 2006 on the common system of value added tax” in the case of the provision of a service. In the case of a provision of tangible goods, the invoice must include the phrase: “VAT exempt – art.138 of EU Council Directive 2006/112/EC of 28 November 2006 on the common system of value added tax”.

Invoices need to be sent both electronically to:
accounting@enoll.org and projects@enoll.org.

??????

The logo for the European Network of Living Labs, featuring a yellow speech bubble shape with the text "European Network of Living Labs" inside.

Invoices need to be sent via post to the following address:
ENoLL iVZW
attn. Director
Kunstlaan 6, 1210 Sint-Joost-ten-Node, Brussels, Belgium.

Article 5

All invoices shall be paid by ENoLL within thirty (30) days after confirmation of receipt of invoice. In case of non- or late payment of an invoice, all amounts shall bear interest at a rate conform the applicable legal provisions from the date on which such amount has become due and payable.

Article 6

During the period of execution of the assignment as described in article 1 of this Agreement, the External Expert shall procure that it has adequate insurance in place to cover the obligations and liabilities under this agreement to the seconded personnel, including but not limited to civil liabilities and work-related accidents outside the scope of existing coverage of ENoLL.

Article 7

ENoLL becomes automatically, without any compensation being due and without any further act being required, the sole owner of all intellectual property rights on the results achieved by the External Expert in the execution of this Agreement.

Article 8

Due to the nature of the activities carried out by the assigned personnel from the External Expert, all business or technical information, either from ENoLL or a third party, (including, but not limited to marketing plans, financial information, specifications, drawings, sketches, models, samples, software or documentation) is considered confidential and of property of ENoLL.

The External Expert must treat the information confidentially and may only use it with a view to providing the activities as specified in the contract. The External Expert also agrees that nothing of this information may be disclosed to any third party if not in relation to the delivery of the contract tasks or by previous agreement with ENoLL. Furthermore, disclosure of any such information is only admissible under fulfilling of all following conditions: (i) they are engaged in the performance of the Services, (ii) they have a need to know for the Services, (iii) they are informed of the confidential nature of the information, (iv) they agree to be bound by terms no less stringent than the ones set forth in this Contract.

The confidentiality obligations stemming from this Contract bind every Party for the duration of the Contract and for a period of five (5) years after the date of termination of this Contract.

Article 9

ENoLL iVZW may terminate the Agreement, if:

??????

European
Network of
Living Labs

- The External Expert is not performing his/her tasks pursuant to the Agreement or to satisfactory standards;
- The External Expert has committed:
 - i. Substantial errors, irregularities or fraud or
 - ii. Serious breach of obligations under the Agreement
- The External Expert has been found guilty of grave professional or civil misconduct, proven by any means;
- ENoLL deems that the tasks assigned to the expert under the Agreement are no longer needed.

The External Expert may terminate the Contract, if it deems that is not, or will not be able to fulfil its obligation to implement the work required (see article 2). The External Expert must formally notify the reasons why and the date the termination will take effect. This date must be at least 15 working days after the notification. If no reasons are given or if ENoLL considers that the reasons do not justify termination, The Agreement will be considered to have been terminated improperly which may lead to the rejection of fees or expenses (see article 3 and 4).

In the event of a dispute arising out of or relating to this contract, including any question regarding its content, validity or termination, the parties will abide by the relevant Belgian legislation and institutions.

Article 10

ENoLL reserves the right to ask the External Expert for compensation for damages that were a result of the wrongful implementation of the Agreement or due to the incomplete or insufficient delivery of the activity agreed upon this agreement.

Article 11

Unless otherwise agreed, all notifications and announcements in the frame of this Contract may be made in writing, or by electronic means if the receipt of the electronic message can be duly confirmed by the other Party.

The nullification of any of the stipulations of this Contract does not affect the validity of the remaining stipulations. If required, the Parties shall undertake to replace the invalid stipulations by a valid stipulation that corresponds as closely as possible to the joint intention of the Parties and the spirit of the present Contract in general.

This Contract represents the entire understanding and agreement of the Parties and supersedes all prior communications, agreements, and understandings relating to the subject matter hereof. The provisions of this Contract may not be modified, amended, nor waived, except by a written instrument duly executed by both Parties.

The signature of a Party via a scanned or digitalised image of a handwritten signature (e.g. scan in PDF format) or an electronic signature (e.g. via DocuSign), shall have the same force and effect as an original handwritten signature for the purposes of validity, enforceability, and admissibility. Each Party received a fully executed copy of the Agreement. Delivery of the fully executed copy via e-mail or via an electronic signature system shall have the same force and effect as delivery of an original hard copy.

??????

**European
Network of
Living Labs**

The Parties agree that all provisions of this contract shall apply retroactively to the contract's effective date to govern all activities relating to the execution of the agreed upon assignments.

Executed in Brussels in two original copies, each party acknowledging the receipt of one.
Executed remotely through two digital or scanned copies, each party acknowledging the receipt of one.

For The External Expert,

For ENoLL iVZW

Name: xxx
Title:
Date:

Name: Evdokimos Konstantinidis
Title: Chairman of the Executive Board
Date:

Appendix 9 – Template invoice of the External Evaluators

Name of the supplier
Address
VAT number
Reg number

Bank name
SWIFT/ BIC
Bank account number

ELECTRONIC INVOICE

Invoice Number:

CUSTOMER

European Network of Living Labs ivzw
Belgium, BE-1210 Brussels
Kunstlaan 6
Customer EU VAT number: BE0824 793 473

Payment method: **bank transfer**
Completion date:/2022
Issue date:/2022

Due date/2022

Description	Qty	Price	Net Price	VAT	VAT Value	Total
The application evaluation of the VITALISE LLs within WP11, TIVALISE Project, Grant Agreement no 101007990 Contract Number:	1	30 euros	30 euros			30 euros

Total 30 euros

VAT exempt - art 44 of EU Council Directive 2006/112/EC of 28 November 2006 on the common system of value-added tax.

Signature for approval

Appendix 10 – Infopack for TA

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101007990.

Project Acronym:	VITALISE
Project Title:	Virtual Health and Wellbeing Living Lab Infrastructure
Project Number:	101007990
Topic:	Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme INFRAIA-02-2020 Integrating Activities for Starting Communities
Type of Action:	RIA - Research and Innovation action
Start date of the Project:	April 2021
Duration of the Project:	36 months

- Reporting Transnational Access - Infopack for Visiting Researchers

(Version 1.0, 22/03/2023)

Disclaimer: The information in this document reflects only the author's views and the European Community is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained therein. The information in this document is provided "as is" without guarantee or warranty of any kind, express or implied, including but not limited to the fitness of the information for a particular purpose. The user thereof uses the information at his/ her sole risk and liability.

Copyright message: ©VITALISE Consortium, 2021. This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both. Reproduction is authorised provided the source is acknowledged.

Reporting Transnational Access – Factsheet for Visiting Researchers

Table of Contents

TABLE OF CONTENTS	2
ABBREVIATIONS	3
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	4
1 INTRODUCTION	5
1.1 THE VITALISE PROJECT	5
2 BEFORE TA	7
3 DURING TA	8
4 AFTER TA	9

D11.3 Evaluation procedure and accepted proposals

Reporting Transnational Access – Factsheet for Visiting Researchers

Abbreviations

EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
H2020	Horizon 2020 Program of the European Commission
RIL	Research Infrastructure Leader
TA	Transnational Access
WP	Work Package

Reporting Transnational Access – Factsheet for Visiting Researchers

Executive Summary

Through the Transnational Access (TA) Programme, VITALISE project opens up 17 Living Lab Research Infrastructures located in 7 different countries to external researchers from multiple disciplines, so that they conduct their research studies for free.

During in-person Transnational Access, researchers will receive financial support for travel subsistence and daily allowance. Each Infrastructure has an estimated access time of 30 days (unit of access) for each project.

The purpose of this factsheet is to illustrate to the visiting researchers to the Living Labs of the VITALISE Consortium all the documents, reports and questionnaires that will be produced before, during and after the Transnational Access Period.

Whereas not otherwise specified, all the documents listed in this factsheet are mandatory in order to access to reimbursement.

1 Introduction

1.1 The VITALISE Project

Researchers in the Health and Wellbeing domain need:

- 1) convenient access to research infrastructures,
- 2) direct engagement of people in order to validate hypotheses, co-design solutions and services, evaluate their feasibility and effectiveness and participate in the translation and mobilization of outcomes and
- 3) experience from multidisciplinary domains (e.g., healthcare management, assistive technologies, data science) to deal with the complexity of health and wellbeing research.

Over the last few years, **Living Labs** have emerged as **resilient research and innovation infrastructures** and have proved to be **key to the integration of research and innovation processes in real life settings**, focusing primarily on people and their engagement in research procedures.

VITALISE opens up Living Lab Infrastructures as a means to facilitate and promote research activities in the Health and Wellbeing domain in Europe and beyond by enabling in-person Transnational Access to **17 Living Lab research infrastructures** and by **supporting remote digital access to datasets** (Virtual Access) of rehabilitation, transitional care and everyday life activities through harmonized processes and common tools.

VITALISE will design and develop ICT tools for shared access of similar devices and applications used across Living Labs, as well as for collecting, storing and sharing datasets.

Lastly, VITALISE will invest in the development of Training methods towards the wider understanding and valorisation of Living Lab methodologies in the research community.

2 Transnational Access

VITALISE project provides access to infrastructures in the Health and Wellbeing domain through 3 Open Calls. Through transnational access (TA), teams of one or more researchers (up to 5 researchers in total) will have the opportunity to propose and conduct research studies in one of the available infrastructures. The TA is planned to be fully in-person, partially remote (i.e., a period in-person and a period of remote access to the infrastructure's facilities) or fully remote. During the in-person TA the researchers will benefit of a financial support for travel subsistence and daily allowance, while there will be no refund during the remote period. For each Infrastructure there is an estimated access of 30 days (unit of access) for each project (up to 5 researchers). Visiting researchers will be directly supported by the Living Labs in the preparation, implementation, and follow-up of transnational access period. The following professionals will be involved in this task:

- **The Research Infrastructures Leader (RIL)**, is the main reference person that will help in planning, preparation, implementation and follow-up of the Transnational Access period.
- **The Living Lab facilitator** will help engaging the local communities in native language whenever local stakeholders' involvement is needed. Per unit access we include the preparatory work and the on-site support.

The research team will have to produce documents, reports and questionnaires, before, during and after TA in order to access to reimbursement. In Table 1 you can have an overview of the documentation for TA.

D11.3 Evaluation procedure and accepted proposals

Reporting Transnational Access – Factsheet for Visiting Researchers

Before TA	During TA	After TA
1. Contract Agreement	1. Fast Track Training Programme	1. Evaluation Questionnaire
2. Bilateral Agreement (Optional)	2. Questionnaire FTTP	2. TA Final Report
3. Expectations Questionnaire	3. NoteTheBook (optional)	3. Exploitation Potential Questionnaires (x2)
	4. TA Log Report	4. Reimbursement
	5. Reminder Receipts	5. Data Anonymization

Table 1: Overview of the documentation to be produced for Transnational Access

In the following section, you will find some additional information on how to produce this documentation.

Reporting Transnational Access – Factsheet for Visiting Researchers

3 Before TA

Before the beginning of the TA period, you will be required to provide the following documentation:

1. Contract Agreement for Transnational Access

In order to access to the Living Lab, you will be required to sign a Contract Agreement (CA).

The CA will be stipulated **between your home organization** (represented by its Legal Representative) **and the VITALISE Consortium** (represented by the Project Coordinator).

The Research Infrastructure Leader will get in touch with you to collect all the necessary information and to sign the contract.

2. Bilateral Agreement (Optional)

In some cases, the Living Lab might ask you to sign a bilateral agreement before the start of the TA: this document is optional, and its stipulation depends on every organization's internal regulation.

3. Expectations Questionnaire for TA

The Living Lab will share with each visiting researcher the link to an expectation questionnaire, to be filled in online on the EUSurvey Platform before the beginning of the TA period.

Reporting Transnational Access – Factsheet for Visiting Researchers

4 During TA

During the TA period you will be required to perform the following actions:

4. **Fast Track Training Programme (FTTP)**

In order to ensure that the research conducted within the framework of the VITALISE Transnational Access Programme is of high quality, any researcher that is accepted for Transnational Access to the Living Lab Research Infrastructures of the VITALISE project, undergoes a fast track training.

The Fast Track Training program includes **two activities**: one before Transnational Access and one on-site. More specifically:

1. Before the actual visit in the infrastructure the researchers have to prepare and submit an **ethical application** in the local ethical committee with the support of the local researchers. The external researchers that propose a new research protocol, are obliged to acquire an ethical approval from the local ethical committee, if the proposal is accepted, prior to their visit.
2. The on-site fast track training lasts approx. 2 days and are realised on the Living Lab Research Infrastructure that the external researchers has been granted access to. This **training provides** the researcher with **all the required information** in order to understand the specific infrastructure, the personnel and the communication channels, as well as how to access the infrastructure.

5. **NoteTheBook (optional)**

The NoteTheBook is an optional platform that can be used to interact with the FTTP study material. The overarching idea behind the NoteTheBook platform is that interacting with the study material by means of taking notes, highlighting texts, sorting out ideas and concepts, marking paragraphs, rewriting sentences in our own words is one of the most commonly and most effectively used techniques for learning.

The NoteTheBook platform allows its users to interact with study texts and then to print the complete study materials including the interactions they made (by note taking, highlighting, etc.) into a personalized PDF booklet.

6. **Evaluation questionnaire for the Fast Track Training Programme**

The Living Lab will share with each visiting researcher the link to the questionnaire, to be filled in on the EUSurvey Platform after you completed the Fast Track Training Programme

7. **Research Log**

The research log is an **online form**, through which you will **report the advancement status of your research project**.

The Research Log has to be filled in on a **daily basis by each visiting researcher** all throughout the duration of the TA period.

Each week, the Living Lab will share with you a new link that you will use all throughout the week. The Research Log is hosted on EUSurvey Platform.

8. **Receipts**

In order to receive the reimbursement after the end of TA, remember to **collect and store all the receipts, tickets and any other evidence of expenditure** related to your daily allowance and travel.

Reporting Transnational Access – Factsheet for Visiting Researchers

Eligible costs include national and/or international **travels** from the external researchers' institution **to the research facility** for each period of occupancy, and **daily subsistence** for each day of occupancy of the research facility (including weekends and public holidays) according to facility providers rules. The expenses incurred by the visiting researchers during TA will be reimbursed according to the normal internal rules and procedures of the Living Lab Research Infrastructure providers, as long as the total costs do not exceed the total available budget.

Finances to cover TA visits have the following limits per person (average flat rate):

- Travel: max €500 travel
- Housing and subsistence: max €100/day

Exceptions to these rules or limits need prior confirmation in writing by the RIL. Therefore, after the publication of the results, the selected researchers will be put in contact with the RIL, to discuss all the detail of the TA, including the expenses covered.

5 After TA

After the TA period you will be required to provide the following documentation **within 1 month** after the end of TA:

9. Final Report TA

The Living Lab will share with you the **Final Report TA template**: you will have to fill it and return it to the Living Lab by email. Remember to declare in the Final Report that you will anonymize the collected data within 6 months.

10. Exploitation Questionnaires

You will be asked to complete **2 exploitation questionnaires**. The links to the questionnaires are both available on the Final Report TA template.

- The first one is an online questionnaire that you can complete directly on the EUSurvey Platform. https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/VITALISE_IR_TAs_VAs
- The second one is an excel sheet: download it, fill it in and return it to the Living Lab by email.
<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1IsJCIVNrGs55tvIuweOG9Iwq3qHiJk6/edit#gid=522290238>

11. Data Anonymization

Remember to perform the Data Anonymization **within 6 months** after the end of TA.

12. Reimbursement

The **expenses will be reimbursed after you submitted the Final Report, the receipts and the questionnaires**. Receipts of tickets for travels, accommodation and living expenses must be attached to claims, which will be made on the facility provider's standard Travel Claim forms. Depending on the internal rules and procedures of the Living Lab Research Infrastructure providers, the claims for daily subsistence might be made on the provider's forms at the daily rate applicable at the time. Remember to check procedures and timing for reimbursement with the Research Infrastructure Leader.

Appendix 11 – Template certificate of attendance to TA and FTTP

CERTIFICATE OF ATTENDANCE

This is to certify that

has successfully participated to the Transnational Access activities and completed the Fast track training programme of the "LiCalab Living & Care Lab" Research Infrastructure as part of the VITALISE Horizon 2020 funded project.

EVDOKIMOS KONSTANTINIDIS

VITALISE Project
coordinator

Operations manager of
Living Lab

VITALISE project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101007990

Appendix 12 – Declaration for TA cancellation

Declaration of Cancellation of Transnational Access Project

I, _____, as Research Infrastructure Leader of _____, declare that the research team related to the project _____ and represented by the leading applicant _____, renounced to Transnational Access, as reported in the email attached to this declaration.

Date, Venue

The Research Infrastructure Leader

Appendix 13 – Addendum to the CA for TA

Addendum to the Contract Agreement for Transnational Access no. _____

I, _____, as Leading Applicant for the project _____ to be deployed in the Research Infrastructure _____, declare that the original research team selected for Transnational Access is hereby amended as it follows:

Withdrawal of the following team member(s): _____

Addition of the following new team member(s), namely:

- 1) Name _____ Surname _____, gender _____, Nationality _____, E-mail _____, Telephone Number _____, position in the affiliated institute _____.
- 2) Name _____ Surname _____, gender _____, Nationality _____, E-mail _____, Telephone Number _____, position in the affiliated institute _____.
- 3) Name _____ Surname _____, gender _____, Nationality _____, E-mail _____, Telephone Number _____, position in the affiliated institute _____.

I hereby declare that the new team member fully complies to all the eligibility criteria established by the VITALISE Consortium for Transnational Access, as described in the *VITALISE Project's Application Manual to the Open Calls for Transnational Access to Research Infrastructures and for Virtual Access to the VITALISE database*.

Date, Venue

The Leading Applicant

The Research Infrastructure Leader

Addendum to the Contract Agreement

Appendix 14 – Application Manual V4.1: VA section updated

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101007990.

Project Acronym:	VITALISE
Project Title:	Virtual Health and Wellbeing Living Lab Infrastructure
Project Number:	101007990
Topic:	Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme INFRAIA-02-2020 Integrating Activities for Starting Communities
Type of Action:	RIA - Research and Innovation action
Start date of the Project:	April 2021
Duration of the Project:	36 months

VITALISE Project's Application Manual to the Open Calls for Transnational Access to Research Infrastructures and for Virtual Access to the VITALISE database

(Version 4.1, November 2023)

Disclaimer: The information in this document reflects only the author's views and the European Community is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained therein. The information in this document is provided "as is" without guarantee or warranty of any kind, express or implied, including but not limited to the fitness of the information for a particular purpose. The user thereof uses the information at his/ her sole risk and liability.

Copyright message: ©VITALISE Consortium, 2021. This document contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both. Reproduction is authorised provided the source is acknowledged.

7 Application procedure for Virtual Access

In order to apply for VA, it is not necessary to undergo a selection process. The applicant(s) should use the application toolkit that provided to:

- Provide personal data of the applicant(s);
- Confirm compliance to the established eligibility criteria;
- Briefly describe the objective of their research and how long they need to access the datasets.

At the end of the procedure, they will receive credentials for accessing the VITALISE database.

7.1 Eligibility criteria for Virtual Access

To apply for VA it is not necessary to undergo a selection process as the applicants will only have to meet the following eligibility criteria:

- They should work in an institution established in a Member State of the European Union or in a state associated to the H2020 Programme [Check the [List of countries eligible for funding](#)]. Researchers working in other countries can apply but they cannot represent more than 20% of the total number of researchers (unit of access?) that will access the VITALISE facilities.
- They cannot have Russian or Belarusian origin.
- They must disseminate the results acknowledging the source of the data (see paragraph 8).
- If the application is submitted by a master's student, at least 1 member of the team must hold a master degree and act as supervisor of the TA.
- If the research team also includes an undergraduate/bachelor student, the leading applicant should be either a professor or a postdoc affiliated to a University or Research Centre.

As explained in paragraph 7, the applicants will have to confirm their compliance to the listed eligibility criteria, assuming responsibility for truthfulness, and as no feasibility and scientific evaluation is required, after completing the submission, they will receive credentials for accessing the VITALISE database and start the VA.

7.2 Virtual Access Application Toolkit

The VITALISE Project's VA Application Toolkit is an online form available on the VITALISE Discovery Portal, which ensures researchers access to research datasets provided by the Living Labs partners of the project. The Application Toolkit is structured in a 4 steps registration procedure: at the end of it, applicants will receive their credentials to access to the datasets. During the registration procedure, applicants will be required to:

- Provide data on their affiliation
- Provide their general data
- Declare their compliance to the previously listed eligibility criteria
- Briefly describe the purpose of the research they will be using the datasets

The VA Application Toolkit is available through the following link: <https://vitalise-portal.iti.gr/>

Application Manual for Transnational Access

7.2.1 Administrative Form

In the first step the applicant is required to provide the following data:

- Details of applicant(s) affiliation:
 - o **name, website, address, country, research background;**
- Number of applicants (select up to 5)**, and for every applicant:
 - o **Username, name, gender, nationality, email, telephone number, position held in the affiliated institution.**

The screenshot shows a web form titled 'Welcome to the VITALISE Project's Virtual Access Application Toolkit!'. Below the title is a short introductory paragraph. The main section is 'Applicant(s) Affiliation:' and contains several input fields: 'Organisation *', 'Website', 'Address *', 'Country *', 'Research background*' (a dropdown menu), 'If you selected 'Other', please clarify.', and 'Number of applicants in the research team*' (a dropdown menu). A blue 'Next' button is positioned below the last two fields. At the bottom of the form area are three small grey circles, with the first one filled, indicating the current step in a multi-step process.

Figure 8 Administrative Details (Affiliation)

Application Manual for Transnational Access

The screenshot shows a web form titled "Application Manual for Transnational Access". At the top, there is a dropdown menu with the number "2" and a downward arrow. Below this, the form is divided into two sections: "First Applicant (User Group Leader/Reference person)" and "#2 Applicant". Each section contains a series of text input fields for "First Name", "Last Name", "Gender", "Nationality", "Email", "Phone", and "Position held in the affiliated institution/organisation*". At the bottom of the form, there is a blue "Next" button and three small grey circles, with the first circle being filled, indicating the current step in the process.

Figure 9 Administrative Details (Applicants)

7.2.2 Eligibility criteria

In the second step, applicants will be required to check all the boxes in order to declare their full compliance to the eligibility criteria previously described in paragraph 7.1.

Application Manual for Transnational Access

The screenshot shows the VITALISE Project's Virtual Access Application Toolkit. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the VITALISE logo, links for Features, FAQs, and About, and buttons for Login and Register. The main content area is titled "Welcome to the VITALISE Project's Virtual Access Application Toolkit!". Below the title, a paragraph explains that the project provides effective and convenient access to research datasets. The "Eligibility Criteria Check" section contains six items, each with a checked checkbox:

- I work in an institution established in a Member State of the European Union or in a state associated to the H2020 Programme*
Not sure? Check the List of countries eligible for funding in this [link](#).
- At least 80% of my research team members works in a Member State of the European Union or in a state associated to the H2020 Programme*
- Neither me nor any of my team members have Russian or Belarusian origin?*
- I am willing to comply with the obligation to disseminate the results, acknowledging the source of the data*
For more information regarding the valorisation procedure, please advise Paragraph 8 of the [Application Manual](#).
- The User Group Leader/Supervisor holds an academic title of at least Master Degree level*
- If my research team also includes undergraduate/bachelor students, the leading applicant is a professor or postdoc affiliated to a University or Research Centre.*

At the bottom of the form, there are "Previous" and "Next" buttons, and a progress indicator with three dots, the first of which is filled.

Figure 10 Eligibility criteria

7.2.3 Project Description

In the third step, applicants are required to provide a short description (max 2000 characters) of the purpose of their research and on how they are going to use the datasets. Moreover, applicants will declare for how many days they will need access to the datasets, and that they will adequately disclose any use of the VITALISE datasets in any resulting scientific publication.

Application Manual for Transnational Access

VITALISE Features FAQs About Login Register

Welcome to the VITALISE Project's Virtual Access Application Toolkit!

VITALISE Project provides effective and convenient Access to the research datasets that were selected during the project's Joint Research Activities, as well as to the ICT tools and e-infrastructures that will support access, curation and analysis of this data. You may use this toolkit to submit your application to request access to our data.

Project Description

In this section, please briefly describe the research and purpose for which you will be using the datasets.

MAX 2000 CHARACTERS

How long do you need access to the VITALISE datasets for?*

Please enter the number of **days** you need to access the data.

Number of Days *

I declare that I will adequately disclose any use of VITALISE datasets in any resulting scientific publication.*

Previous Next

● ● ●

Figure 11 Project description

7.2.4 Application Overview and Final Submission

In this final page, applicants will choose a password for their account and provide confirmation on the completeness and correctness of the information provided. By pressing a dedicated button, the registration procedure will be completed and they will immediately be able to login in the discovery portal and access the datasets.

Application Manual for Transnational Access

Figure 12 Application overview and submission

7.3 Applicants' obligations for Virtual Access

The applicants who meet all the criteria to apply for VA, after receiving the credential for accessing the VITALISE database, will have the only obligation to disseminate the knowledge they will generate from the access free of charge to the VITALISE database (see paragraph 8) and they will be asked to fill out a satisfaction questionnaire.